

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	11	19	Itajaí, Brasil	S	26	54.615	W	048	39.137
End	2021	11	27	Buenos Aires, Argentina	S	34	36.449	W	058	22.080

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this campaign was to research Santa Marta Cape coastal area, south of Santa Catarina State, as it is a region with frequent occurrence of upwellings, but poorly studied. However, as Tara could not be stopped in the region, but sailing towards Buenos Aires, it was decided to study three distinct areas in this region of the Western South Atlantic, (1) Santa Marta Cape, aiming to sampling a possible upwelling event, (2) a truly oceanic area, under the influence of the Brazil Current, and (3) an area under the influence of Prata River, where Veleiro ECO will carry out a more detailed survey next year. The focus of study for this campaign was in the epipelagic zone, from the DCM to the surface.

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Samuel Audrain
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves Tournon
3	CREW - Mecano	Leo Boulon
4	CREW - Deck	David Monmarche
5	CREW - Deck	Allain
6	CREW - Cook	Carole Pire
7	CREW - Media	Marin
8	GUEST - Artist	Edson Macallini
9	GUEST - Observer	
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Thomás
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Emmanuel Boss
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Lee Karp-Boss
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Gleice Santos Souza
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Andrea Green
15	SCIENCE - F - additional	

SAMPLING STRATEGY & ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

We performed three stations,

- (1) Santa Marta Cape - #056 – shallow station (56 m depth) and close to the coast. We did two depths, Z00 - surface and DCM – 15 m depth. Our intention was to sample a water column under influence of an upwelling event.
- (2) Oceanic area - #057 – deep station (1.700 m depth). We did three sampling depths Z00 - surface, Z02 – DCM (65 m) and Z04 – 300 m.
- (3) Prata River Plume - #058 - shallow station (50 m depth), close to the coast and near the Brazil-Uruguay border. We did two depths, Z00 - surface and DCM – 27 m depth. Our intention was to sample a water column under influence of Prata River Plume.

We've got on the station # 058 around 8:30h (UTC). Before we started, we decided to check the images of phytoplankton community (Imaging Flow Cytobot - IFCB) and also surface chlorophyll and salinity measurements with the equipment LISST Horizon. By surface map chlorophyll it looked like we were in a very productive area, but we didn't. So I've decided to navigate towards the coast in order to search for Prata River Plume. Phytoplankton community started to change bit by bit, chlorophyll increased and salinity dropped. After 2:30h of navigation we reached our sampling point – our scientific target for sampling.

The research team was satisfied with the work performed. It was a big challenge for everyone, especially in the first station (#056), as none of the researchers knew the protocols in depth and we didn't have time for a pilot station. It is noteworthy that our campaign was the first without Doug on board, who knew by heart all the protocols that would be executed. Thus, we choose to simplify the sampling strategy.

Figure 1. Sampling station's location. Station 1 – 056, Station 2 – 057 and Station 3 - 058.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

The vertical profiles of the water column, as well as the images of the surface phytoplankton community, show the differentiation between the sampling stations.

We did not see an upwelling event in Santa Marta, probably due to the influence of southerly winds in the days prior to sampling.

Figure 2. Station #056 Vertical Profile

Figure 3. Station #057 - Vertical Profile

Figure 4. Station #058 - Vertical Profile

Santa Marta
#056

Oceanic area
#057

Plata River Plume
#058

Figure 5. Phytoplankton community registered in surface waters of the three sampling stations by the Imaging Flow Cytobot.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Provide an overview of sampling activities on every day of the Campaign, indicating the number of deployments done for each type of event.

Station ###	Date, start YYYY-MM-DD	Latitude, start N dd.dddddd	Longitude, start E ddd.dddddd	UDW - Aerosols	UDW - Biogeochemistry	BGC – CAST – 0-1000	SML	SRF – PUMP	SRF – NET – WP11 20	SRF – NET – WP11 200	SRF – NET – Manta 330	EPI – CAST – 0-200	EPI – NET – WP11 20	EPI – NET – WP11 200	EPI – Régent 680	MESO – CAST – 0-1000	CAST – Trace Metals	VMP – Profile	TIA – Towed Array	BowPole	hTSRB
056	2021-11-20	S 28° 41.088	W 048° 42.921	X	X			X			X	X	X	X	X				X		
057	2021-11-22	S 31° 01.412	W 48° 51.231	X	X			X				X	X	X							
058	2021-11-24	S 33° 06.448	W 051° 59.453	X	X			X				X	X	X						X	X

TIA were deployed from the first to second station, during navigation. From the 20th at 22:13h to 22th 08:28h (UTC).

The trawls with the 20, 200 and 680 nets were all oblique, from the DCM to the surface.

We could not deploy the Manta Net in stations #057 and #058, sea was very agitated.

We did not make horizontal surface hauls with the 20 and 200 um nets. It was my mistake - Andrea Green.

SCP50	petri-slide											
F200	250-mL-bottle	4										
E200	15-mL-falcon						3					
S200	5-mL-cryotube									3		
S200-L	5-mL-falcon						3					
PM-HG200	Zip-lock	3										
MB200	4-mL-Vial						3					
CP200	petri-slide	3										
F680	250-mL-bottle	3										
F2000	250-mL-bottle											
E680	15-mL-falcon						3					
S680-L	MULTIPLATES						3					
E2000	15-mL-falcon						2					
AI	petri-slide	12										
AS	2-mL-cryotube											12
AF	Zip-lock						12					
SP300	2-mL-cryotube											6
MP300	2-mL-cryotube											
CP300	petri-slide	2										
TOC	30-mL-bottle											
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube											
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube											
S025-L	15-mL-falcon						5					
S520-L	5-mL-falcon						6					
FM5	5-mL-falcon				10							
MTE-BP	125-mL Bottle											
	TOTAL	75			47		137			69	42	33

MTE-T (Bottle 125ml, RT > 10C) = 3 samples (Protocol B2)

PS I didn't distinguish between the boxes from RT+10, FRG+4 and FRZ-20, only from LN#1, 2 and 3.